
**THE INFLUENCE OF EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT ON
INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOR IN EMPLOYEES GEN Z SPECIAL
REGION OF YOGYAKARTA WITH WORK LIFE BALANCE AS AN
INTERVENING VARIABLE**

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Abstract

The study aims to analyze the effect of employee engagement on innovative work behaviour with work life balance as an intervening variable. This research uses Incidental sampling technique with total of 65 respondents with the criteria of Gen Z employees aged 18-26 years who live and work in the Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta. The test used in this study are descriptive analysis, instrument test (validity test and reliability test), classical assumption test, coefficient of determination, hypothesis test (t test), and path analysis using the sobel test. The independent variable in this study is employee engagement. The intervening variable in this study is work life balance. The dependent variable in this study is innovative work behavior. The results of this study indicate that, employee engagement has positive and significant effect on work life balance, work life balance has positive and significant effect on innovative work behavior, employee engagement has positive and significant effect on innovative work behavior, and work life balance partially mediates the relationship between employee engagement and innovative work behavior.

Keywords: Employee Engagement, Innovative Work Behavior, Work Life Balance.

INTRODUCTION

The development of Human Resources Management has now changed to Human Capital Management, more commonly abbreviated as HCM, is a very common one in the among Human Resources practitioners. Human Capital is an intangible asset (intangible), human capital is not owned by the company that employs it, and usually cannot be exchanged for other types of capital. Abel and Deitz, 2012 in (O'Mara & Greenberg, 2023). Human resources are no longer a supporting factor but rather company assets that have a role in achieving organizational goals, people are now considered a company asset that must be maintained, because Humans are the driving force and determinant of the future course of an organization provide returns.

Digital transformation has now entered the industrial revolution 5.0 with the development of technology which is now increasingly sophisticated, with this transformation human resources are required to be able to follow and take advantage of these changes so that human resources remain competent and productive so that companies are more effective and efficient in achieving goals. One of the problems that cannot be separated from the business world is resource competition, with competition, innovative work behavior must be raised. Competition and innovation are two things that cannot be separated from business. In a competitive environment, globalization and rapid technological change, Innovation is an important facilitator for business growth. Innovation is important for companies to win the market and achieve sustainable development goals, so innovation work behavior needs to be raised (Rao Jada et al., 2019).

Every company is obliged to maintain its human resources so that they can make the best contribution as part of the process of achieving company goals, which can be realized through employee engagement. Employee engagement is a closely intertwined physical, cognitive, and emotional involvement between a person and their role in a job. Employee engagement is an effort made by the company in binding its employees to remain loyal. In this case, employee engagement has the potential to facilitate employees innovative work behavior. An employee does not only live in the work environment. Employees have a role outside the workplace to balance their role at work. Work life balance is a term used to describe the balance between ones work and life. The concept of work life balance is built on the idea that work life and personal life complement each other in bringing balance to one's life. Work life balance is something that must be highlighted by the company as a form of concern for the personal needs of employees, so that employees can do work more optimally (Malasari, 2022).

Research by Ariawaty, (2019) and Atthohiri & Wijayati, (2021) states that the influence between employee engagement on work life balance is significantly positive. These results means that the higher the employee engagement, the higher the level of work life balance. Wood et al. (2020) explain different results, namely a significant negative effect between employee engagement and work life balance, where the higher the employee engagement, the more unbalanced life outside work. Achieving a healthy work life has been associated with more creative thinking. There are two factors of innovative behavior, namely flexibility and preference for change and novelty. Flexibility is one of the factors that influence innovative behavior. Work life balance owned by individuals is part of flexibility. So that work life balance is also one of the factors that influence innovative behavior (Darmaki & Omar, 2020).

In their efforts to stimulate and promote innovative work behavior among its employees, managers face various challenges such as employee readiness to innovation, disparities in the work environment, and the fact that differences in organizational culture can inhibit the generalization of behaviors that encourage innovation (Tan et al., 2021).

Gen Z is advised to understand the importance of work life balance. Gen Z is often referred to as a generation that values the importance of flexibility. An organization ability to provide a flexible work life and meet the needs of work life balance is an important factor in attracting Gen Z. Work life balance is one of the main priorities and preferences Gen Z wants an organization after a career and an opportunity to share and help other people (Agarwal & Vaghela, 2018). Innovation is an embedded character within Gen Z and is a catalyst for achieving organizational innovation. As An innovative generation, Gen Z longs for renewal from the organizations they work in work and expect a harmony of values and an innovative work style (Han, 2020).

Based on this description, researchers are interested in conducting research with title "The Influence of Employee Engagement on Innovative Work Behavior Gen Z Employees in the Special Region of Yogyakarta with Work Life Balance as a Variable Intervening".

TEORITICAL BACKGROUND

Employee Engagement

Employee engagement is psychological attachment so that emotionally connected employees tend to have good relationships, experience empathy towards line managers and colleagues, seeing that they are cognitively bound to know which ones they truly

consider their mission and role in work environment. Employee engagement is a thing that exists very important as a reflection of employee behavior (Ariawaty, 2019). Engagement can be increased if employees feel safe to showing and empowering himself, feeling himself useful and valuable to company and has sufficient resources to carry out its role. In to measure employee engagement, measuring tools or indicators are needed to measure it for employee engagement. Indicators for measuring employee engagement according to Bakker et al. (in Nadialista Kurniawan, 2021) as follows: vigor, dedication, and absorption.

Work Life Balance

Work life balance is a person's ability to balance the two life, namely work life and personal life. Work life balance is possible is defined as an effort to create a healthy and supportive work environment, and allows workers to have space to balance work and personal activities so that they can increase employee loyalty and output work (Larastrini and Adnyani, 2019). Work life balance is a state of balance for managing activities in life without neglecting their responsibilities in workplace and all aspects of his personal life. The main role of work life balance is creating balance in work, which will hopefully ensure that Employees not only spend their time working, but also enjoying it his personal life (Arifin and Muharto, 2022). Indicators for measuring work life balance according to Greenhaus et al. (2003) as follows: time balance, involvement balance, and satisfaction balance.

Innovative Work Behavior

Innovation is the process of discovering or implementing something new into a new situation. Innovative work behavior or innovative work behavior includes exploration of opportunities and generalization of new ideas (behavior that related to creativity), but innovative work behavior can also include behavior directed toward implementing change, applying new knowledge, or improving personal and business-oriented performance processes implementation of these ideas into their work (Jong and Hartog, 2008).

This is in line with the definition of innovative work behavior put forward by Janssen (in Febriani, 2019). Janssen explained that innovative work behavior is the deliberate creation, introduction and implementation of new ideas in work role, group or organization, which aims to obtain role benefits performance, group, or organization. This is like a more precise fit in between appreciation of job demands and worker resources, increases job satisfaction, and better interpersonal communication. According to Jong and Hartog (2008) explain the existence of four dimensions or indicators of innovative work behavior, including: idea exploration, idea generation, idea championing, and idea implementation

Hypothesis Development

Previous research states that employee engagement and work life Balance is one aspect that needs special attention company. This reason is strengthened by evidence that employee engagement and work life balance that is implemented well can increase innovative work behaviour.

The Influence of Employee Engagement on Work Life Balance

Research by Iqbal et al. (2017) and Ariawaty (2019) explain that employees Engagement affects work life balance positively and significantly. This matter reinforced by Atthohiri and Wijayati (2021) also stating that the influence between Employee engagement on

work life balance has a significant positive effect. This shows that the balance a person has in work life balance can be weaken/strengthen depending on the level of engagement of each employee. Based on this description, the following hypothesis can be formulated:
H1: Employee Engagement has a positive and significant effect on Work Life Balance.

The Influence of Work Life Balance on Innovative Work Behavior

Wan and Liu's (2020) research found that three balance factors work life: work-family balance, work-vacation balance, and job growth balance all have a significant positive correlation with innovation. This shows that the higher the work life balance employees, the more innovative behavior they can promote in the process Work. This is confirmed by Qomaruzzaman et al. (2023) also found that work life balance has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behavior. Based on this description, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H2: Work Life Balance has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior.

The Influence of Employee Engagement on Innovative Work Behavior

Vithayaporn and Ashton (2019) explain that an employee is involved have positive enthusiasm in his work. They are willing to be creative and innovate according to the theory of creativity as a basis for innovation. Engaged employees who have a pattern Positive thinking is more positive at work showing helpful and oriented behavior on service. Frontline employees have the opportunity to be creative work in an innovative way such as solving problems in a way that different, providing customer service in creative ways. Considering nature engagement, it is reasonable to assume that engagement is related to behavior innovative. Guzman Pedraza et al. (2016); Vithayaporn and Ashton (2019); and Ariasih et al. (2023) found that employee engagement has a positive effect on innovativeness work behavior. This is confirmed by research by Ajie and Nugroho (2023) which also states that employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behaviour. Based on this description, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H3: Employee Engagement has a positive and significant effect on Innovative Work Behavior.

The Influence of Employee Engagement on Innovative Work Behavior through Work Life Balance

Al-Ajlouni (2021) discovered and advocated the relevance of employee engagement in encouraging innovative work behavior of employees. Research that has been carried out by Ali et al. (2022) has empirically validated the direction of employee engagement causality and work life balance and concluded that employee engagement is an antecedent from work life balance and this research finds that work life balance mediates partially the influence between employee engagement and innovative work behavior. Matter This shows that work life balance has a direct impact on innovative work behavior of employees and the indirect influence of innovative work behavior in influencing employee engagement. Based on the description above shows that innovative work behavior is influenced by employee engagement which is high when employees have work life balance, then hypotheses can be formulated as follows:

H4: Employee Engagement influences Innovative Work Behavior mediated through work life balance.

Figure 1: Research Framework

METHODS

This research will look at the Influence of Employee Engagement on Innovativeness Work Behavior with Work Life Balance as an Intervening Variable. Population of This research includes all Gen Z employees who live and work in the region Yogyakarta Special. The sampling method uses non-probability sampling with Accidental Sampling. Data in the form of Gen Z perceptions obtained as many as 65 respondents using a questionnaire and measured using a Likert scale of 1 to 5. Data analysis uses instrument tests, classical assumption tests, regression tests, and tests Sobel test. The statistical procedures used used SPSS version 22.

RESULTS

Validity and Reliability Test Results

From the results of the validity test on Gen Z employees in the Special Region of Yogyakarta, all valid questions which include employee engagement, work life balance, and variables innovative work behavior. The results of the validity test on the items for all variables shows that all items in each variable are completely "valid".

Reliability Test Results

From the results of reliability tests on Gen Z employees in the Special Region of Yogyakarta It is known that all variables are declared reliable. This is proven by the value Cronbach's alpha > significance level (0.70). Reliability test results on employees Engagement has a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.796, on work life balance has a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.746, and innovative work behavior has a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.841.

Classic Assumption Test Results

Normality test

The regression model either is a normal or near normal data distribution. Normality testing on This research used the Komogorov-Smirnov test. Residuals are normally distributed if the significance level is greater than 0.05. Normality test on Gen Z employees in Yogyakarta Special Region variables employee engagement, work life balance, and innovative work behavior is normally distributed, that is, it has a higher level of significance from 0.05.

Linearity Test

The Linearity Test aims to see whether the model specifications used are is correct or not. The basis for decision making in the linearity test is, if the F value calculate < F table and the significance value for linearity is > 0.05, then there is a linear relationships significantly between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Linearity test on Gen Z

employees in the Yogyakarta Special Region employee variables engagement, work life balance, and innovative work behavior have a linear relationship significantly linear between the independent variable and the dependent variable.

Heteroscedasticity Test

A good regression model is one with homoscedasticity or heteroscedasticity does not occur. From all the output it can be seen that the dots are not forms a clear pattern, and the dots spread to the left and right of the number 0 on X axis and spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. So you can It was concluded that there was no heteroscedasticity problem in the regression model.

Hypothesis testing

The t statistical test basically shows how far the influence of one explanatory/independent variable individually in applying variations in the dependent variable. The test uses a significance level of 5% or 0.05. The t test is carried out with the criteria if t count > t table and the significant value is < 0.05 then this means that there is an influence between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Based on the results of the t test in this research using a statistical program IBM SPSS version 22 carried out hypothesis testing as follows:

Table 1. Linear Regression Test Result

Variabel	Koefisien	Std. Error	Sig	Keterangan
X → Z	0,582	0,107	0,000	Signifikan
Z → Y	0,621	0,122	0,000	Signifikan
X → Y	0,528	0,138	0,000	Signifikan

1. Testing the influence between the Employee Engagement variable (X) and Work Life Balance (Z) among Gen Z employees throughout Yogyakarta.

The results of data processing obtained a calculated t value (5.678) > t table (1.998) and a significant value of 0.000 < Level of Significance (0.05). So it is known that there is a significant influence between Employee Engagement on Work Life Balance. Constant and coefficient values shows a positive direction. So it can be said that the Employee variable Engagement has increased, so the Work Life Balance variable has also increased. So it can be concluded that H1 is accepted.

2. Testing the influence between the Work Life Balance (Z) variable and Innovative Work Behavior (Y) among Gen Z employees throughout Yogyakarta.

The results of data processing that the calculated t value (6.289) > t table (1.998) and the value significant 0.000 < Level of Significant (0.05). So it is known that there is an influence significant relationship between Work Life Balance and Innovative Work Behavior. Mark constants and coefficients show a positive direction. So it can be said if the Work Life Balance variable has increased then the Innovative Work variable Behavior also improves. So it can be concluded that H2 is accepted.

3. Testing the influence between the Employee Engagement (X) variable and Innovative Work Behavior (Y) among Gen Z employees throughout Yogyakarta.

The results of data processing that the calculated t value (4.935) > t table (1.998) and the significant 0.000 < Level of Significant (0.05). So it is known that there is an influence significant relationship between Employee Engagement and Innovative Work Behavior. Mark constants and coefficients show a positive direction. So it can be said

if the Employee Engagement variable has increased then the Innovative Work variable Behavior also improves. So it can be concluded that H3 is accepted.

Path Analysis (Sobel test)

Sobel test which aims to determine the calculated t value and significant value which aims to find out the calculated t value and the significant value of no influence direct. To determine the effect of X on Y through Z, the Test concept will be used Sobel (Sobel Test). Path analysis show that Employee Engagement (X) can have a direct influence on Innovative Work Behavior (Y) with a regression coefficient value of 0.528. Meanwhile, it can have an indirect effect namely Employee Engagement (X) towards Innovative Work Behavior (Y) through Work Life Balance (Z) obtained by multiplying the regression coefficients is $0.582 \times 0.621 = 0.361$. This shows a more indirect influence through Work Life Balance is smaller compared to the direct influence of Employee Engagement towards Innovative Work Behavior, it can be concluded that the Work Life variable Balance was accepted as a partial mediating variable. Next to find out the significance or not, tested using the Sobel Test as follows:

$$a = 0.582 \quad Sa = 0.107$$

$$b = 0.621 \quad Sb = 0.122$$

Calculation of the standard error of the indirect effect coefficient is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} Sab &= \sqrt{b^2Sa^2 + a^2Sb^2 + Sa^2Sb^2} \\ &= \sqrt{(0,621)^2 \cdot (0,107) + (0,582)^2 \cdot (0,122)^2 + (0,107)^2 \cdot (0,122)^2} \\ &= \sqrt{0,004395 + 0,005012 + 0,000168} \\ &= \sqrt{0,009575} \\ &= 0.097851 \end{aligned}$$

This the t test value can be obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} t &= \frac{ab}{Sab} \\ &= \frac{0,361}{0.097851} \\ &= 3,6892 \end{aligned}$$

From these calculations it is known that the resulting t value is 3.6892 which is greater than t table 1.998 with a significance level of 0.05, meaning that the parameter This mediation is significant, so it can be said that Work Life Balance mediates the influence of Employee Engagement on Innovative Work Behavior. With Thus H4 is accepted.

DISCUSSION

This research was conducted on Gen Z employees aged 18-26 years who live and worked in the Special Region of Yogyakarta with a total of 65 respondents. Technique This data was collected using Accidental Sampling because the population cannot be known surely. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires via Google form which is then analyzed. Based on the analysis carried out then the following results

were obtained:

The Influence of Employee Engagement (X) on Work Life Balance (Z)

Based on the test, data processing obtained a t count of 5.678 > t table is 1.669. And the significance value is 0.000 < 0.05. Constant values and the coefficient shows a positive direction. So it is known that there is a positive influence and significant relationship between employee engagement and work life balance. So that it can be concluded that H1 is accepted.

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Iqbal et al., (2017), Ariawaty, (2019), and Atthohiri & Wijayati, (2021) explain that employees Engagement has a positive and significant effect on work life balance. This shows that the balance that a person has in work life balance can be weakening/strengthening depending on the level of engagement of each employee, increasingly High employee engagement means balance between work and life as well will experience an increase.

The Influence of Work Life Balance (Z) on Innovative Work Behavior (Y)

Based on the test results, data processing obtained a t count of 6,289 > t table is 1.669. And the significance value is 0.000 < 0.05. Constant values and the coefficient shows a positive direction. So it is known that there is a positive influence and significant relationship between work life balance and innovative work behavior. So that it can be concluded that H2 is accepted.

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Ali et al., (2022) and Qomaruzzaman et al., (2023) show that work life balance has an effect positive and significant towards innovative work behavior. This shows that increasingly The higher an employee's work life balance, the more innovative behavior there is they can promote in the work process.

The Influence of Employee Engagement (X) on Innovative Work Behavior (Y)

Based on the test, data processing obtained a t count of 4,935 > t table is 1.669. And the significance value is 0.000 < 0.05. Constant values and the coefficient shows a positive direction. So it is known that there is a positive influence and significant relationship between employee engagement and innovative work behavior. So that it can be concluded that H3 is accepted.

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Guzman Pedraza et al., (2016), Vithayaporn & Ashton, (2019), Ariasih et al., (2023), and Ajie & Nugroho, (2023) shows that employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on innovative work behavior. It explains that an engaged employee has positive enthusiasm in his work. They are willing to be creative and innovate accordingly creativity theory as a basis for innovation. Frontline employees have a chance to be creative in their work in innovative ways such as solving problems in a different way, provide customer service in a different way creative.

The influence of Employee Engagement (X) on Innovative Work Behavior (Y) mediated by Work Life Balance

Based on the results of the research that has been carried out, the results show that the influence directly from employee engagement to innovative work behavior of 0.528. Meanwhile, the indirect influence from employee engagement to work life balance of 0.582 and from work life balance to innovative work behavior of 0.621. So The indirect effect is obtained by multiplying 0.582 by 0.621, namely of 0.361. This shows an indirect influence through work life balance is smaller compared to the direct influence of employee

engagement towards innovative work behavior. And from the Sobel test calculations it is known that the valueThe resulting t is 3.6892 which is greater than the t table of 1.669 at the significance level 0.05, meaning that the mediating parameter is significant, so it can be said that Work Life Balance partially mediates the influence of Employee Engagement towards Innovative Work Behavior. So it can be concluded that H4 is accepted.

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Al-Ajlouni, (2021) discover and advocate the relevance of employee engagement in encouraging innovative work behavior of employees. Research conducted by Ali et al., (2022)found that work life balance partially mediates the influence between employees engagement towards innovative work behavior. This shows that work life balance causes employees to have innovative behavior that they can promote in the work process such as solving problems in different ways, providing creative customer service that can mediate influence between employees engagement towards innovative work behavior.

CONCLUSION

The results of this research show that employee engagement has a positive effect and significant to work life balance, work life balance has a positive effect and significant to innovative work behavior, employee engagement has a positive effect and significantly towards innovative work behavior, and mediating work life balance partial relationship between employee engagement and innovative work behavior.

It is hoped that the company can improve employee engagement and work life balance so that employees, especially Gen Z, can make the best contribution so that can increase employee innovative work behavior. With innovative work behavior Employees are expected to be able to provide innovation for the company's sustainability.

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